

BEBB

digital
edition

Open Up DSE

DSE Meets Library –
BEBB digital Edition and UB Basel in reciprocal
long-term collaborative Settings, and Beyond

Martin Kurz, Sulamith Gehr

DSE Meets Library (I) - Introduction

Conference Theme:

Use and Reuse of (meta)data of DSEs (Digital Scholarly Editions)

Research Needs

Standards

Aggregation, Linking

POST-PROJECT ACCESSIBILITY
(How?)

Editions' Needs...

Precondition for (Re)Use of Data / Edition:
medium- / long-term Accessibility,
or Preservation of DSE data + hosted Edition with Functionalities.

BEBB

Basler Edition der Bernoulli-Briefwechsel

BEBB digital edition:

Multi-ego, pluricentri, or multilateral epistolary Network of Bernoulli Letters.

Basel-related: The Bernoullis citizens since 1622 from Basel, i.e. 400 years.

Who are the Bernoullis?

Dynasty of Mathematicians, Scientists:

Daniel I, Jacob I, Jacob II, Johann I, Johann II,
Nicolaus I, Nicolaus II, and Jacob Hermann.

Their Correspondents:

Leibniz, Newton, Scheuchzer,
de Tressan, Michelotti etc.,
plus more than 400 Correspondents.

Historical Periods:

Early Modern History, Post-Humanism / Renaissance, Scientific Revolution,
Enlightenment, first Period of Industrialization.

ca. 1650-1820.

The Bernoullis (2)

Family Tree:
Three Generations

(Source: Bernoulli-Euler-Center
(BEZ), Basel)

The Bernoullis and their Topics? (3)

Topics of their Research and for a great part found in their Letters:

Mathematics, Physics, Astronomy, Medicine, Law (+Math.), Theology, Technology, and more ...

Who deals with these Topics and the Bernoullis?

Historians of Mathematics (traditionally), Historians of Science, Historians of Technology

Digital Historians of Science, Digital Humanists

But lately also: Legal Historians.

Not yet or not so much:

(Computer)Linguists, Theologians, Historians of Medicine, Biographers.

But also:

General Public, High School Students and Teachers.

BEBB digital Edition

Definition BEBB – DSE

History of the Basel Edition

8 Phases:

1745-1934 Bernoullis and their Correspondents: 1745 **Johann I with Leibniz**

1935-1993 **Otto Spiess**

2005-2015 Media-Wiki

2016-2018 Varignon

2018-2021 **BEOL**

2021-2024: TEI-XML

2024 BEBB **TEI Publisher digital edition** (5400 Letters, at least the metadata)

2025-2028: all letters edited and published on BEBB digital edition,

new: Web Annotations Tool

Re-Evaluation of BEOL (Bernoulli Euler Online)
and **OBE** (Opera Bernoulli Euler, Gerd Grasshoff)

DSE meets Library (II)

Our case:

Paradigmatical?

Long-term Collaboration beginning in the Era
of only physical Resources, successfully developed
into one operating in the digital-only Space,
with Benefits for the *Edition*
as well as the *Library*,
its general Users and Researchers.

DSE Meets Library (III) –

BEBB digital edition and UB Basel in reciprocal long-term collaborative settings, and beyond

Basel Edition Bernoulli Letters BEBB
close Cooperation with
University Library Basel.

Reciprocity, Synergy.

What is the role of the University Library
in the context of DSEs?

Medium and long-term timescales?

Layers of Investigation:

Metadata

IT Infrastructure

Organisational, Facilities

Funding, Science Policy Issues

BEBB

digital
edition

BEBB institutionnel:
BEZ, Dep. Mathematics
University of Basel
University Library
SNF, SAGW

BEBB Personnel:
Director: H. Harbrecht
Editors: S. Gehr,
M. Kurz, F. Nagel
Assistants: M. Stettler,
R. Germann, E. Kacł

External Data Pools:
GND, GeoNames

Digital Images
iiif

BIBB
5400 Letters

BEBB
Bernoulli Letters

Several 100 Letters
Correspondents:
Newton, Euler,
Du Châtelet, Tressan,
Scheuchzer, et al.
Goal: all 5400 Letters

TEI-XML /
TEI Corpus

TEI Publisher
internal / external

Oxygen XML
Editor

Github
Repository
existdb

OA, FAIR

Cooperations:
UB Basel
Euler Edition
Leibniz Archive
Op. Bernoulli Euler

Long-term Aspects of Cooperation

Context of centuries-old institution.

UB Basel Strategic Directions.

UB Specialty: Responsibility for development and maintenance of Swisscollections.

Basel Bernoulli Letters Inventory (BIBB) in Swisscollections
<https://swisscollections.ch/Bibliographien/BibliographiesSpecial>

Cantonal bibliographies Special bibliographies

The special bibliographies list publications on individual persons and special subject areas. For the respective research fields, the special bibliographies offer an important source, since in addition to monographs, literature such as articles etc. on corresponding persons or topics is also listed.

— **Bernoulli-Briefinventar (BIBB)**

- + Bernoulli, Daniel I (1700-1782)
- + Bernoulli, Daniel II (1751-1834)
- + Bernoulli, Jacob I (1655-1705)
- + Bernoulli, Jacob II (1759-1789)
- + Bernoulli, Johann I (1667-1748)
- + Bernoulli, Johann II (1710-1790)
- + Bernoulli, Nicolaus I (1687-1759)
- + Bernoulli, Nicolaus II (1695-1726)
- + Hermann, Jacob (1678-1733)

+ **Gottfried Keller-Bibliographie**

Benefits for the Edition

All-encompassing Facilities.

Purchase of Bernoulli estates from Gotha and Stockholm, discovered by Otto Spiess.
Preservation and Digitization of the Letter Manuscripts and Bernoulli Archive.

Linking, Platforms.

Long-term Maintenance (Metadata).

Accessibility and (Re)Usability of (Meta)Data for Purposes of the Researchers.

Enhanced Visibility and Discoverability.

Special Metadata Knowledge of Library Experts.

Benefits for the Library

Similar Goals of the Edition and of the Library.

More research-driven Data.

BIBB Inventory Basis for re-cataloguing of Library's Manuscripts.

Use and Transformation of Library Holdings.

Cooperation (Metadata): How? Phases? (2)

Transformation from Print to digital, the latter in two Phases,
from Media-Wiki to BEOL to TEI Publisher (XML) digital Edition.

1) Compilation of Bernoulli Letter Inventory (BIBB), i.e. metadata of 5400+ Letters transferred to the Library (meta)catalogue of archival collections (HAN) 1997-2003.
Customized search mask for the BIBB.

2) Online edition as a combination of library catalog and digital letter texts presented in a MediaWiki format (www.ub.unibas.ch/bernoulli), the latter developed by UB IT.

3) Rebuilding of HAN and ingestion into Swisscollections.
New customized search tree for the BIBB (<https://swisscollections.ch/Bibliographien/BibliographiesSpecial>).

4) Merging of the BIBB and Bernoulli-MediaWiki into a TEI XML based edition (until now), BEBB digital Edition.

Challenges of Cooperation

040 |a CH-001880-7 |b ger |e HAN-Katalogisierungsregeln
 046 |a s |c 1676.09.19
 046 |a s |c 1676.09.29
 1001 |a Bernoulli, Jakob |d 1655-1705 |0 (DE-588)118509950 |e Verfasser |4 aut
 2451 0|a Brief an Peter Werenfels |c von J[acob I] Bernoulli
 250 |a Abfertigung
 264 0|a Dabam Genevae |c 19/29 VIIbris ao 1676.
 300 |a 2 Bl. |c 16,5 x 20,5 cm
 336 |b txt |2 rdacontent
 337 |b n |2 rdamedia
 337 |b c |2 rdamedia
 338 |b nb |2 rdacarrier
 338 |b cr |2 rdacarrier
 351 |c Dokument=Item=Pièce
 490₁ |a Bernoulli-Archiv. I, Briefe von den Bernoulli. Jacob (1654-1705), Briefe von Jacob I Bernoulli (1654-1705) |v 1
 500 |a Das zweite Blatt diente als Briefumschlag und trägt Siegel sowie Adresse
 506 |a Es gelten die generellen Benutzungsregeln für den Sonderlesesaal
 541 |f Öffentliche Bibliothek der Universität Basel
 546 |a Lateinisch
 581 |a Druck: Jac. B. Briefe, pp.201-202
 5830 |a Datenimport aus LIDOS / Bernoulli (2004-07-02)
 583₁ |b Verzeichnung=Description=Inventaire |c Juli 2023 |f HAN-Katalogisierungsregeln |i Revision nach Vorlage |k nni
 655 7|a Handschrift |2 gnd-content
 655 7|a Autograf |2 gnd-content
 655 7|a Briefsammlung |2 gnd-content
 7001 |a Werenfels, Peter |d 1627-1703 |0 (DE-588)124314805 |e Adressat |4 rcp
 7001 |a Bernoulli, Jakob |d 1655-1705 |0 (DE-588)118509950 |4 scr
 751 |a Genf |0 (DE-588)4020137-5
 830₀ |a Bernoulli-Archiv. I, Briefe von den Bernoulli. Jacob (1654-1705), Briefe von Jacob I Bernoulli (1654-1705) |v 1 |w (HAN)000079889DSV05
 8524 |b A117 |c 117B2 |j - |9 (41SLSP_UBS)9972432845105504
 852₄ |b A100 |c 102HSS |j UBH Archiv Bernoulli Ib, Jacob (1654-1705), Nr.1 |9 (41SLSP_UBS)9972432845105504
 85641 |u http://dx.doi.org/10.7891/e-manuscripta-163716 |z Online via e-manuscripta

Accommodating Edition Metadata
in a System designed to Needs of
Library Catalogue and its Users.

Integration through Python-
scripted exporting Process of the
BIBB Inventory Records
(MARC21 into TEI-XML).

[https://swisscollections.ch/Record/
991170514611905501?sid=124539182](https://swisscollections.ch/Record/991170514611905501?sid=124539182)

BEBB

digital
edition

Result of Cooperation on Editorial Side

BEBB-UB Cooperation – a symbiotic Working Model?
Building a long-term Research Infrastructure

Presentation of BEBB digital Edition based on TEI Publisher

Going live now for the first time! 25 January 2024.

BEBB TEI Publisher Edition online! Potentials for Development.

The screenshot displays the BEBB digital edition interface for a letter by Johann Bernoulli. The interface is divided into several sections:

- Header:** BEBB logo and navigation links like "About" and "Previous letter".
- Metadata:**
 - Autor:** Bernoulli, Johann
 - Adressat:** Tressan, Louis Elisabeth de la Vergne
 - Ort:** Basel
 - Datum:** 1759.08.12
 - Originaldatum:** Bâle ce 12. aoust 1759
 - Sprache:** French
 - Standort:** Universitätsbibliothek Basel, Handschriften
 - Signatur:** UBH L Ia 676:Bl.242-245
- Text:**
 - Fussnote:** Am Briefkopf eigenhändig: "à M. le C.te de Tressan". Am Schluss von der Hand Joh. III B.s: "La présente est copiée Cay.B. n.5"
 - Druck in:** Erw.: Otto Spiess: Das Grab von Maupertuis in Dornach. In: Freiwillige Basler Denkmalpflege, Jahresbericht 1937, S. 39-53. - SA, 2
 - Entstehungsstufe:** concept
 - Physische Beschreibung:** 4 Bl., 21,5cm x 17,5cm
 - Download-Link XML** and **Link zum Digitalisat** (both with external link icons)
 - Brief-ID:** B_1759-08-12_991170516783305501
- View Options:** A dropdown menu for "View" set to "textnahe Fassung".
- Text Content:** The beginning of the letter: "Bâle ce 12. aoust 1759 M. Ce n'est pas une petite consolation pour moi dans mon malheur de voir que des personnes comme vous s'occupent de moi...".
- Image:** A thumbnail of the original handwritten letter manuscript.
- Page Info:** "1 : Page 242r" and a language selector set to "English".

Apart from Library Integration/Hosting – further Potentials for **Development:**

Aggregators: EMLO (also Library based), CorrespSearch. Metagrid.

Historicised Geo Data: HistoGIS, EM Places.

Linguistic Pre-processing of Letter Texts: NLP.

Edition Platform specifically designed for **Mathematical Editions.**

BEBB-UB Cooperation may be paradigmatic Working Model.

Application of **AI/ML/LLM** Tools.

Building a long-term Research Infrastructure (DSE-UB-Sources Online-DaSCH).

BEBB digital edition:

<https://bebb.jinntec.de/home.html>

Online available since 25 January 2024

In the Future: bebb.unibas.ch

Letter of Johann II Bernoulli
to the Comte de Tressan

Link to example: https://bebb.jinntec.de/B_1759-08-12_991170516783305501

Resume of our Collaboration

In all the phases.

Physical (print), hybrid, to digital Edition:

Media-Wiki

BEOL

To the most recent

TEI Publisher Edition.

Support of Library essential with mutual Benefits.

Technical and infrastructural Challenges all solved and sustainable.

Approach: Through **Merging** of Expertise and **inter-institutional** Cooperation.

Similar Approaches to Renew Role of the Libraries

Cornelia Bögel, *Digitale Editionen als Zukunftsaufgabe für Bibliotheken und Forschung*. 2013.
(functional and institutional rapprochement between libraries and the research community, cf. abstract)

Elena Pierazzo, *Digital Scholarly Editing*, 2015.

Elina Leblanc, *Design of a Digital Library Interface [...]*, 2018.
(envisage common interface for both resources [digital library and DSE], cf. abstract)

Christiane Fritze, *Wohin mit der digitalen Edition? [...]*, 2019.
(Collections and existing Expertise)

Andrea Malits, *Infrastrukturentwicklung für digitale Editionen [...]*, 2020.
(Science-driven networks of expertise, p. 209, transl. M. Kurz)

Andreas Kränzle, Gerold Ritter, Christian Sieber,
***Sources Online - eine nachhaltige Infrastruktur [...]*, in: *ABI Technik* 2023; 43(3): 158-167.**
(Public heritage institutions best suited in Cooperation with technical service providers, p. 164, translation M. Kurz)

Essential Stakeholders / Participants in the wider DSE Network:

Library and Science Policy Makers,
(Digital) Humanities Scholars,
DSE Community,
General Public

Swiss Academies
SAGW
SNF

Swiss-
universities
(ORD?)

DaSCH

National Library (NL)?
ETH? CERN?

DARIAH-[CH]
[WG DSE]

(NEW: Swiss Competence Network DSE)

Beyond Switzerland? EU?

BEBB
digital
edition

Univ. Library
Basel

Sources Online

Jinntec (Software Dev.)

BEZ (Bernoulli-
Euler-Center)

University
Basel

DH Labs
ZDE / RISE

e-editiones

Inspiring Visions

Future?: Digital Infrastructure Library Services for Hosting (UB and/or NL, ETH)
together with Sources Online and DaSCH (Integration in Digital Library).

Hosting Services of Editions at the National/University Library where Manuscripts are held.
Inspired by model example of the Austrian National Library.

Digitale Editionen an der Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek

An der Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek wird eine übergreifende Infrastruktur für digitale Editionen aufgebaut. Alle künftigen digitalen Editionen, die auf Quellenmaterial der Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek basieren, werden in dieser realisiert. Die Infrastruktur weist verschiedene Komponenten sowohl für die Erstellung als auch für die online Präsentation auf, die modulartig an jede digitale Edition angepasst wird. [Mehr ...](#)

Digitale Editionen

Wenzelsbibel Digital

Peter Handke: Notizbücher

Supported by Sources Online,
local DHLabs, IT Departments.

Building a collaborative, federative
Structure.

Coordinated by Swiss National Library
(NL)?
and DaSCH?

<https://edition.onb.ac.at/o:ode.home>

Acknowledgements

SAGW

Jinntec: Helena Bermudez Sabel, Magdalena Turska, Lars Windauer, Wolfgang Meier

RISE University of Basel: Elena Spadini, Eric Decker

University Library Basel: Director, Special Coll. Dep., IT

BEZ (Bernoulli-Euler-Centre)

DaSCH

DHLab University of Basel

BEBB Team

Director of BEBB Project: Helmut Harbrecht

Fachgremium BEBB

OpenUpDSE24 Organizers: Elena Spadini, Yann Stricker

Your Inputs

Questions & Answers

CONTACT

bebb@unibas.ch

martin.kurz@unibas.ch

sulamith.gehr@unibas.ch